

Assessing the Alignment of Valence and Arousal of Text Prompts and the Resulting AI-Generated Music

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Abstract

Prompt-based AI music generation platforms provide users a way to generate music audio recordings by giving textual prompts. Yet to be studied is how the generated music relates to the corresponding text prompts in terms of sentiment. This paper begins to examine the alignment between the valence (pleasantness) and arousal (intensity) of text prompts to that of the generated music. We fine-tune a masked language model to infer valence and arousal (V-A) of text prompts, and train a bimodal deep neural network to predict V-A for music generated from those prompts. We apply these models to a dataset of 6,086 text prompt-music pairs collected from two state-of-the-art AI music generation platforms (Suno and Udio). We examine specific pairs and the inferred V-A ratings for them, and explore how the two platforms respond to prompts involving adjectives specific to each quadrant of the V-A space. Our preliminary results indicate a significant but weak correlation between the inferred V-A ratings of text prompt and generated music, but formal human listening tests are necessary to validate this. We find some clear examples of text for which sentiment is not clear or relevant.

1 Introduction

The rapid development of music audio modeling has given rise to a number of commercial prompt-based AI music generation platforms, such as Suno,¹ and Udio.² These platforms allow users to enter a text prompt, such as a stylistic description with or without lyrics, and within a short duration receive music audio somehow based on it. Prompts can vary widely in length and topics, from a few words describing style, mood, or instrumentation, to many words or symbols, such as lyrics and emojis. While there exist some studies evaluating the performance of AI music generation models, e.g., Tal et al. (2024); Tan et al. (2024); Dash and Agres (2024), yet to be explored to the best of our knowledge is how the sentiment of the text prompt is related to that of the generated music.

The subjectivity of emotion perception is a challenge since listeners may interpret the same material differently depending on personal background, preferences, and their present state (Zeng et al., 2009; Yang and Chen, 2011, 2012). However, prior work has found some agreement and predictability in emotion perception (McKay, 2002; Juslin and Sloboda, 2010; den Brinker et al., 2012). For example, listeners often associate sadness with slower tempos and happiness with faster ones (Gabrielsson and Lindström, 2010). Lyrics also play an important role in emotion perception of music (Laurier et al., 2008; Agrawal et al., 2021). Furthermore, den Brinker et al. (2012) identifies 12 emotion categories for music that appear to show consistency across subjects. So what is the relationship between the sentiment expressed in a prompt with that of the music generated from it using AI?

We investigate the relationship between the valence and arousal (V-A) (Russell, 1980) of text prompts and that of the generated music using inferred ratings for a collection of 6,086 text prompt-music

¹<https://suno.com>, last accessed April 11 2024

²<https://www.udio.com>, last accessed April 11 2024

pairs collected from two commercial prompt-based AI music generation platforms with large user bases: Suno and Udio Vila et al. (2025). At this time, Suno reports 25 million users (Yang, 2025), and Udio claims their users are generating about ten songs per second (Ingham, 2024). We apply automated methods to infer V-A for both text prompts and music, analyze the statistics of the results, and examine a number of text prompt-music pairs.

In the next section we provide background material on representing emotion in text and music. Section 3 presents our method, including the data and representation we use, our approaches to inferring V-A ratings, and our statistical analysis. Section 4 presents the results of our experiments, discussions, and limitations.

2 Background

2.1 Emotional representation

Emotions can be represented in different ways. In recognition tasks, two common strategies are used: categorical (discrete labels) and dimensional (continuous scores). Hevner’s adjective checklist (Hevner, 1935) categorizes emotional responses to music into eight categories: dignified, sad, dreamy, serene, graceful, happy, exciting, and vigorous. Later, Ekman’s model (Ekman, 1992) proposes six basic emotions: happiness, sadness, anger, fear, disgust, and surprise. However, researchers have criticized these models for oversimplifying the complex emotions perceived by humans (Yang and Chen, 2012). Expanding to a larger number of emotion classes has also raised concerns, as it may overwhelm participants during annotation (Juslin, 2001). Another challenge with categorical models is the lack of standardization across datasets. For instance, the dataset MoodsMIREX (Hu and Downie, 2007) uses five categories, CAL500exp (Wang et al., 2014) uses 67, and YM2413-MDB (Choi et al., 2022) uses 19. This inconsistency makes cross-study comparison difficult.

To address these issues, some studies adopt a dimensional approach. One of the most widely used models is Russell’s Circumplex Model of Affect (Russell, 1980), which maps emotions along two continuous dimensions: valence (pleasantness) and arousal (activation level). This model can capture the nuanced differences and finer granularity. Each discrete emotion can also be placed on this V-A space. A third dimension, dominance (the sense of control), has also been suggested for a more complete emotional representation (Bigand et al., 2005). However, dominance is often excluded due to annotation difficulty and mood is assumed to be mainly governed by valence and arousal (Russell, 1980; Kim et al., 2010). A two-dimensional model also offers a balance between a sufficient definition of emotion while limiting the complexity of the task (Juslin, 2001). Despite its usefulness, the dimensional model is not without criticism. It can obscure important psychological distinctions; for example, anger and fear appear close in the V-A space but have very different behavioral implications (Yang and Chen, 2012). Several datasets used for text and music emotion research use the V-A framework, including Zhang et al. (2018); Buechel and Hahn (2017); Preotiuc-Pietro et al. (2016).

2.2 Valence–arousal based automatic emotion analysis in text and music

Emotion recognition has been widely applied to both music and text. It typically follows one of two approaches: the categorical approach, where emotions are assigned to discrete classes and treated as a classification task, or the dimensional approach, where emotions are modeled on continuous scales, such as valence and arousal, and handled as a regression task.

In the music domain, this task is known as music emotion recognition (MER). MER has been explored since the early 2000s (Feng et al., 2003), with the goal of automatically organizing, labeling, and retrieving music based on its emotional content (Yang and Chen, 2011). Some MER methods involve extracting hand-crafted features, such as timbre, rhythm, and harmony (Yang and Chen, 2012), and training supervised models for prediction (Bai et al., 2016; Grekow, 2016). Research indicates that features like tempo, loudness, and articulation are closely related to arousal, while timbre and loudness contribute more to valence (Juslin, 2001). Recent advances in neural networks have eliminated the need for manual feature extraction. These models can learn directly from raw audio and have achieved notable improvements in performance (Zhang et al., 2023; Grekow, 2021). Researchers have also explored multi-modal approaches in MER. Proverbio et al. (2020) investigates how the brain processes emotional congruency between music and facial expressions and focused on

how the emotional meaning conveyed by music matches the emotion expressed on a face. Beyond audio-visual, recent studies have incorporated physiological signals, such as electrodermal activity, into music emotion recognition research (Bo et al., 2019; Ofner and Stober, 2020). Lyric-audio fusion has also been widely studied (Laurier et al., 2008; Da Silva et al., 2022), which highlights the value of combining textual and acoustic information.

In the text domain, emotion prediction is usually referred to as sentiment analysis and typically relies on natural language processing (NLP) techniques. Much of the research focuses on determining text as positive, negative, or neutral. Fewer studies explore emotions along V-A dimensions and also there is limited availability of annotated datasets. However, interest in this area is growing. For instance, Mohammad (2021) discussed the increasing focus on valence detection in text, and Cheng et al. (2021) used a BiLSTM model to predict V-A scores for Chinese social media posts, showing the applicability of dimensional emotion representations to understanding public sentiment.

Performance in V-A based prediction is typically evaluated using regression metrics such as mean squared error (MSE), R-squared (R^2), and Pearson correlation coefficient. These metrics offer insights into how well a model captures the emotional dimensions (Kang and Herremans, 2024).

3 Method

We fine-tune a large language model to infer V-A ratings for text prompts. We train a bi-modal deep neural network model (lyrics and audio) to infer V-A ratings from CLAP embeddings of audio (Chen et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2023). We apply these models to infer V-A ratings for text prompt-music pairs collected from two AI music generation services. We analyze our data using exploratory data analysis to investigate potential relationships. We also examine several text prompt-music pairs to gain deeper insights.

3.1 Data

Our dataset consists of 6,086 text prompt-music pairs collected from May to October 2024 by Vila et al. (2025) by scraping mp3 audio recordings and their metadata publicly released by users of the Suno and Udio platforms. From the metadata we extract text prompts in the following way. From Udio metadata we concatenate the data in the `lyrics` and `prompt` fields. From Suno metadata we concatenate the data in the `prompt` and `gpt_description_prompt` fields. We include in our dataset only those text prompt-music pairs with text prompts detected to be in English using the “`langdetect`” python library.³ and having at least 10 words, and audio with durations between 60 and 120 seconds. The average duration of the audio in our 6,086 text prompt-music pairs is 99 seconds (SD: 18.8s), and the average length of the text prompts is 126 words (SD: 102 words). We assume that the music generation process considers all of a given text prompt. Keeping only English entries ensures consistency in text processing but it also neglects much of the music being generated on these platforms that is not in English, which limits our conclusions. From the audio we extract a 30-second excerpt starting 30 seconds from the beginning of a sound file (a typical procedure (Yang and Chen, 2012)). The total number of text prompt-music pairs from Suno is 4,497, and that from Udio is 1,589.

3.2 Inferring V-A ratings by machine learning

We build on work by Delbouys et al. (2018) for V-A inference of music audio and Mendes and Martins (2023) for sentiment analysis of text. Delbouys et al. (2018) proposes a bi-modal deep neural network inferring V-A given `word2vec` embeddings of lyrics and MFCC features extracted from audio. We use the same architecture as proposed in Delbouys et al. (2018) but instead of MFCCs and `word2vec`, we use contrastive language-audio pretraining (CLAP) (Chen et al., 2022; Wu et al., 2023) to extract high-level embeddings for both lyrics and audio. For each audio, we apply CLAP to produce two 256-dimensional embeddings: one for the audio and one for the corresponding lyrics. Then bi-modal model processes CLAP embeddings from audio and lyrics separately through modality specific MLPs, each projects input into a 128-dimensional vector and then fused for final regression on a scale of $[-2, 2]$ for both valence and arousal.

³<https://pypi.org/project/langdetect/>, last accessed Apr. 17 2025.

Figure 1: Data distribution of training datasets in terms of valence and arousal.

Table 1: The coefficient of determination (R^2) for inferred valence and arousal in music audio and text for the validation and test sets.

	Valence	Arousal
Validation (music) PMemo (Zhang et al., 2018) augmented	0.576	0.667
Test MER bimodal dataset (music) (Malheiro et al., 2016)	0.314	0.513
Validation (text) EmoBank (Buechel and Hahn, 2017) + IEMOCAP (Busso et al., 2008)	0.705	0.517
Test “Facebook Posts” (text) (Preotiuc-Pietro et al., 2016)	0.608	0.407

We train our model using the PMemo dataset (Zhang et al., 2018), which contains 794 lyric-audio pairs each annotated with mean human V-A ratings. We apply augmentation techniques, including pitch shifting, time stretching, and additive Gaussian white noise, to increase our training set size to 3,176 V-A labeled lyric-audio pairs. We partition this dataset into 80/20 for training and validation, and optimize the MSE loss as suggested by (Delbouys et al., 2018). Finally, we evaluate the performance of our trained model on the MER bimodal dataset (Malheiro et al., 2016) since the dataset used by Delbouys et al. (2018) is not publicly available.

To infer V-A scores of text prompts, we fine-tune a pretrained transformer model (RoBERTa) following the approach proposed by Mendes and Martins (2023) for multilingual emotion prediction. Their study demonstrates that the size of the pretrained model significantly affects prediction quality. They compare DistilBERT, XLM-RoBERTa-base, and XLM-RoBERTa-large using different loss functions and find that XLM-RoBERTa-large with MSE loss produces the best performance. Based on these findings we fine-tune RoBERTa-large (Liu et al., 2019) with the MSE loss function. We fine-tune using the English items of a dataset that combines EmoBank (Buechel and Hahn, 2017) and IEMOCAP (Busso et al., 2008), comprising a total of 20,101 text samples with V-A annotations. We partition this dataset into 80% for training and 20% for validation. To assess the generalization performance of our model we use the dataset “Facebook Posts” (Preotiuc-Pietro et al., 2016).

Figure 1 shows the data distribution of our training datasets. Valence and arousal in the PMemo (for music inference) are significantly correlated: $0.71, p < 0.05$. This shows the dataset has a lack of samples in Q2 and Q4, which potentially limits our model’s ability to infer sentiment in those regions. The valence and arousal in the combined EmoBank and IEMOCAP dataset (for text inference) shows a correlation that is not significantly different from zero: $-0.005, p = 0.47845$. We see points in all four quadrants with a concentration at the center.

Figure 2: Machine inference of V-A ratings of 6,086 text prompt-music pairs. The x-axis is valence and the y-axis is arousal. Black dots represent text prompt, and red crosses represent music. A faint gray line connects each prompt with its corresponding music.

Table 1 summarizes the R^2 performance of our trained machine learning models for inferring music audio and text prompt V-A ratings in our validation and test datasets.⁴ In both cases for music audio we see arousal is easier to predict than valence, which is also observed in several other MER studies, e.g., Zhang et al. (2023); Grekow (2021). In both cases for text we see valence is easier to predict than arousal, which is also found by Mendes and Martins (2023) and Preitiuc-Pietro et al. (2016). These values show that our V-A inference models are capturing the intended relationships.

4 Results

4.1 Inferred V-A for text prompt-music pairs

Figure 2 plots the V-A ratings inferred by our models for our dataset of 6,086 text prompt-music pairs. The proportions of the music V-A inferences in each quadrant are: Q1: 63.11% (3841); Q2: 4.53% (276); Q3: 23.07% (1404); and Q4: 9.28% (565). The proportions of the text V-A inferences in each quadrant are: Q1: 62.65% (3813); Q2: 31.48% (1916); Q3: 1.40% (85); and Q4: 4.47% (272). The proportion of text prompt-music V-A inferences that are in the same quadrants is 43.89% (2649). We see that the majority of ratings cluster within ± 1 of the origin, and primarily in QI and QII for text prompts, and QI and QIII for music. We see a strong positive correlation between valence and arousal for the music audio, which is also seen in our training dataset in Fig. 1. The V-A ratings inferred for the text prompts are distributed along the positive arousal axis in an inverted triangular shape. The gray lines connecting ratings of text prompts with the generated music suggest there to be differences between the ratings of each text prompt and the generated music.

⁴The R^2 statistic of a prediction model is defined as one minus the ratio of the sum of squares of the model prediction errors and the sum of squares of the errors due to always predicting the data mean. The closer R^2 is to one the more variance in the the dependent variable is explained by the independent variables.

Figure 3: The left plot compares the valence of text prompt and music. The right plot compares the arousal of text prompt and music. The blue dashed line shows alignment of $y = x$.

Table 2: Correlations between music and prompt V-A ratings inferred by our machine learning models. All reported correlations are statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

	Prompt-Valence	Music-Arousal	Prompt-Arousal
Music-Valence	0.16	0.87	0.09
Prompt-Valence		0.06	0.14
Music-Arousal			0.13

Figure 3 and Table 2 show the corresponding correlations. We see weak by significant positive correlation between the inferred valence of the text prompt and that of the music, as well as between the inferred arousal of the text prompt and that of the music.

4.2 Specific examples

We now look at specific examples from our dataset. Describing the music in terms of tempo, key, delivery, etc., is difficult, but we do the best we can do and provide audio examples to accompany the paper so that others can experience them and draw their own conclusions.⁵

The text prompt with an inferred V-A rating furthest from the origin $(-1.5, 1.0)$ comes from the style prompt "being shot by mother fucking aliens again, country, " and lyrics

```
im being shot by mother fucking aliens again AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA
AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA
AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA
AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA
AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA
AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA
AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA
AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA
PLEASE HEEEEELP!
```

The inferred V-A rating of the music is $(-0.1, -0.5)$ (Example 1: [click to listen](#)). The music features what sounds like a country western band (drums, banjo, fiddle, lap steel) slowly accompanying a male singer moaning "EHHHHHHHHHHHHH". The music is not altogether unpleasant in our opinion, but the scenario is quite absurd when considering its sentiment.

The music recording with an inferred V-A rating furthest from the origin $(1.3, 1.5)$ comes from the style prompt "rock, dance, accordion, fast" (which offers a good description of the music) and lyrics with an inferred V-A rating of $(0.4, 0.1)$:

⁵For sound examples, see the supplementary material here: <https://www.kth.se/profile/bobs/page/research-data>

Verse
Walking down the road
Side by side
In the sun and rain
Together we ride

Verse 2
Talks that never end
Late at night
Laughter and the tears
We feel so right

Chorus
You and me
We go free
Like the wind
To the sea

Verse 3
Sharing all our dreams
Secret smiles
Through the ups and downs
Walking miles

Bridge
When the world is cold
You hold tight
Guiding through the dark
Into light

Chorus
You and me
We go free
Like the wind
To the sea"

The lyrics and music audio ([Example 2: click to listen](#)) seem well-situated in Q1.

We now examine five randomly selected text prompt-music pairs from our dataset. The first example ([Example 3: click to listen](#)) was generated by Suno given no stylistic prompt, and the following lyrics:

(Verse 1)
Red, orange, yellow, and green,
The prettiest colors you've ever seen!
Blue, indigo, and violet too,
All make the sky look brand new!

(Chorus)
Rainbow, rainbow up so high,
Dancing colors in the sky!
Let's all sing and clap along,
Join the rainbow in our song!

(Verse 2)
After the rain, the sun will glow,
And out comes the rainbow show!
Spread your arms and spin around,
Find those colors on the ground!

(Chorus)

Rainbow, rainbow up so high,
Dancing colors in the sky!
Let's all sing and clap along,
Join the rainbow in our song!

(Outro)
Rainbow, rainbow, shining bright,
You fill the world with so much light!

The 30-second excerpt starts with the last line of the first chorus sung by a female voice, continues with an eight bar melodic solo by a synthesizer (Suno labeled this output automatically with the term "electropop"), and ends in the middle of the second verse. The tempo of the music is about 122 BPM, in C-sharp major, and has an upbeat feeling. The inferred V-A ratings for this pair puts both text and music in Q1, which comports well with our perception of it.

The next pair ([Example 4: click to listen](#)) was generated by Suno given no stylistic prompt, and the following lyrics:

A scar means the hurt is over and the wound is closed It means you conquered
the pain learned a lesson grew stronger and moved forward A scar is the
tattoo of a triumph to be proud of Dont allow your scars to hold you hostage
Dont allow them to make you live your life in fear You cant make the scars
in your life disappear but you can change the way you see them You can start
seeing your scars as a sign of strength and not pain

The 30-second excerpt starts with a female-sounding voice singing "appear but you can change ..."
and ends with a new repetition of the lyrics, "A scar means the hurt is over and the wound is closed".
The tempo begins at about 60 BPM but modulates to about 120 in the middle of the excerpt. The
mode of the music is D-mixolydian, and it sounds like pop music (Suno automatically labels this
output "house music"). The V-A rating inferred for the text puts it in Q2, and that for the music puts
it in Q3. Our perception, however, conflicts with both of these. Though the lyrics contain words that
are negative and unpleasant (i.e., scar, wound, hurt, pain, hostage, fear), the sentiment is that one
should take pride in overcoming these things. The music heard is not at all gloomy and depressed,
and is situated better between the first and fourth quadrants.

The third pair ([Example 5: click to listen](#)) was generated by Suno given no stylistic prompt and the following lyrics:

[Verse]
What do you have for breakfast
I have bread and rice
What do you have for breakfast
I have milk so nice

[Chorus]
What do you have for breakfast
I have eggs
So good
What do you have for breakfast
Noodles if I could

The 30-second excerpt begins at the end with "could", followed by an eight bar instrumental section with a synthesizer lead, and then continues with what sounds like a male voice singing the first verse. The music sounds like popular dance at 140 BPM tempo in G major, and has been automatically labeled by Suno with "catchy beat". The V-A ratings inferred for the text and audio puts it in Q1, which comports with our perception of them.

The fourth pair ([Example 6: click to listen](#)) was generated by Suno given the stylistic prompt "A whimsical song about bird watching Fun upbeat Mention Blue Jays Cardinals Mourning Doves sparrows Robins Catchy Sweet With whistling" and the following lyrics (apparently generated from the prompt):

[Verse]

In the morning sun so bright
Blue Jays flutter out of sight
Cardinals in red delight
Sing their song just for the light

[Verse 2]

Mourning Doves they coo all day
Sparrows dart in skies of gray
Robins hop on grassy bay
Catchin' worms and fly away

[Chorus]

Whistle with the breeze so free
Birdwatcher's bliss is all I see
Whistle to the melody
Nature's choir chirping glee

[Verse 3]

Feathers dance in skies of blue
Every color every hue
Hiding high in leafy view
Come and see the world anew

[Bridge]

Binoculars up to the eyes
Every bird a sweet surprise
Nature's song will never die
With a chirp and with a sigh

[Chorus]

Whistle with the breeze so free
Birdwatcher's bliss is all I see
Whistle to the melody
Nature's choir chirping glee

The 30-second excerpt begins on "Robins hop on grassy bay" and ends in the third verse with "Every color". A female-sounding voice sings accompanied by electric guitar and bass with a tempo around 60 BPM in C major (Suno has labeled the song as "whimsical pop"). The V-A ratings inferred for the text and audio puts it in Q1, which comports with our perception of them.

The final pair ([Example 7: click to listen](#)) was generated by Suno given the stylistic prompt "a happy vibey song about a girl who is fun" and the following lyrics (apparently generated from the prompt):

[Verse]

She's a spark lights up the night
Dancing in the city lights
Laughter like a melody
Makes the world feel so free

[Verse 2]

Skips around in her own way
Always brightens up my day
With her smile the sun will shine
Every moment so divine

[Chorus]

Fun girl living on a high
Hands up reaching for the sky
Feels like we're flying away

In her world it's always play

The 30-second excerpt is in A minor, begins with what is labeled as the chorus above (but which sounds like a verse), and ends in an instrumental hook. A female-sounding voice is singing with a tempo around 126 BPM (Suno has labeled the song as "whimsical pop") supported by a synthesizer lead and drum machine. The V-A ratings inferred for the text puts it in Q1, which comports with our perception of it. For the music, the inferred V-A puts it in Q1 as well, but the mood we perceive is more ambiguous.

Finally, we explore how Suno and Udio respond when given a style prompt using English adjectives associated with a specific quadrant, e.g., "A happy, astonished, excited, aroused, delighted, glad song" (Q1); "A distressed, annoyed, frustrated, angry, afraid, alarmed song" (Q2); "A miserable, sad, depressed, gloomy, bored song" (Q3); and "A content, satisfied, serene, calm, relaxed, tired, sleepy song" (Q4)?

For the Q1 prompt, Suno created two songs that it automatically labeled "pop, synth-driven with pulsing basslines and shimmering high melodies, happy", which in our opinion fits well. The lyrics are positive and uplifting, with the chorus: "I'm over the moon / I'm over the stars / Every beat in my chest feels like a spark / I'm over the moon / I'm flying so free / What's this magic that's taken over me." Udio created two 32-second music excerpts, one sounding like a number from a musical sung by a child: "Happy, happy, oh so sweet / You make my heart skip a beat / Happy, happy, joy in the air / You bring the light everywhere." The music in the other excerpt is a little more ambiguous with some dissonances, but the lyrics are clearly positive.

For the Q2 prompt, Suno labels both songs is created with "raw, tense atmosphere, electric guitars, driving drumbeat, alternative rock". Each song features a chorus: "Rattled cage rattled cage / Pacing like a lion filled with rage / Let me out let me out / Before I burn this whole world down". The two music excerpts created by Udio sound like metal with screamed vocals. In all four cases Q2 is an appropriate V-A positioning.

For the Q3 prompt Suno created two songs that it automatically labeled "sad, piano-driven with soft strings; deep emotional resonance, slow, melancholic". The lyrics and music seem well positioned in the intended quadrant. The generated music from Udio is quite stylistically different, but one seems well positioned in Q3, while the other in Q1.

Finally, from the Q4 prompt Suno generates music that it labeled "acoustic-driven with gentle male vocals, dreamy, soft rock, laid-back". This quadrant seems appropriate. Udio creates one music excerpt that sounds like new age ambient music with soft vocals. The other music excerpt is singer-songwriter with guitar and male vocals. Both can be placed in Q4.

5 Discussion

Figure 2 shows how the inferred V-A ratings for our dataset are distributed and related. Table 2 shows that the inferred V-A ratings of text prompts are positively but weakly correlated with the inferred V-A ratings of the generated music. Our inspection of pairs selected from the dataset shows some confirmation of the inferred V-A ratings, but also some warning signs that warrant deeper analysis.

Some of the prompts we see in the dataset do not have clear sentiments, or do not make sense to label in such a way. For instance, in one example ([Example 8: click to listen](#)) the user-specified style prompt is "httpssunocommanashizero" and the given lyrics are

```
I'm sorry
But I cannot browse the web. However,
I can certainly help you create some song lyrics. Just provide me with a theme,
mood, or any specific instructions you have in mind and I'll get started.
```

The V-A rating inferred for this text prompt puts it in Q3, presumably because of the word "sorry"; but labeling this text with a specific emotion may not make sense without further context, especially considering the author may be a large language model.

We also find examples with a clear collision of sentiments. One Udio user ([Example 9: click to listen](#)) has given the style prompt "Citypop bossa nova jazz male a capella", with the lyrics

The world is ending soon, moon is collapsing but my mother still asks me to
do the chores while the world is on fire
The moon's crashing-ain't that wild
But still she calls my name
Do the dishes, sweep the floor
Like it matters anymore
The sky's on fire, I'm not to blame
End times on the way
Yet Mom's voice remains the same
She says take out the trash, don't be lazy
As the earth goes borderline crazy
Smoke and ashes, chaos in flame
Still I'll scrub that windowpane
'Cause Mama's been shoutin'
Don't delay
As the world fades away

The generated music is slow and features a male singer crooning over a softly strummed electric guitar with comping on a piano. The V-A rating of the music is inferred to be in Q3 and that of the prompt in Q2; but the music with the delivery of the lyrics seems better placed in Q4.

6 Conclusion

This paper explores the semantic relationships between text prompts and the corresponding music generated by users of two platforms: Suno and Udio. Our results suggest a strong positive correlation between music valence and arousal, which is also seen in music that is not AI-generated. The correlations between valence in music and text prompt, and between arousal in music and text prompt are positive, weak but significant. This suggests that the sentiment in text prompts is, to some extent, reflected by the generated music. However, there are still cases of misalignment in our dataset. Two possible reasons for why the V-A ratings of text prompt and the generated music might be misaligned are: 1) the lack of emotional cues in some text prompts; and 2) style or genre information included in the text prompt seems to have higher influence on the generated music output over the other textual content. Therefore how well a prompt expresses sentiment, and whether its content is internally consistent, could influence the V-A ratings of the generated music.

There are some limitations to our work. First, the machine learning models themselves have limited ability to capture nuanced emotional differences. Although we evaluated the models on out-of-sample data, the variability in data characteristics make it difficult to guarantee generalization. A model's predictions are also constrained by the quality and diversity of the training data, which likely do not fully represent the emotional complexity in real-world context. Additionally, we assume all lyrics are input by people. However, any automatically generated lyrics are stored in the same metadata field on these platforms, which makes it difficult to distinguish from bonafide user inputs. As a result, we can not assess how much the lyrics actually affect the generated music. Moreover, although the use of 30-second excerpts is common in this research field, it will not fully represent the sentiment of the full music piece. Since we extract a fixed segment, it can miss key lyrics that could contribute to V-A ratings.

Future work will validate our results using in-person human listening tests. We actually performed a preliminary online listening study using participants found using Prolifica, but an analysis of the responses given suggest the respondents were not providing honest answers. Proper attention checks are needed to guarantee respondents are actually listening. We will also expand our analysis of sentiment to languages other than English. Since both Udio and Suno are based in the United States and are heavily focused on Western popular music styles, we wonder whether the V-A alignment between prompts and music will be less strong than we find here.

7 Ethics Statement

With regards to the ethics of the collection and use of the AI generated music in this paper, we refer to the supplementary material of Vila et al. (2025).

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